

Improving word recognition of K-2 Chinese children with low oracy/literacy in English language through concrete poetry teaching

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Abstract

This six-month study using the single-group pre-test/post-test research investigated the effectiveness of concrete poetry as a strategy to improve word recognition of ten K-2 Chinese children with low oracy/literacy in English language. Concrete poems (a unique genre of poetry) come in all kinds of shapes, sizes, colours, textures, and even flavours. A concrete poem can be static or dynamic. These K-2 children randomly selected from the preschools were taught to compose their own concrete poems and through them learned to recognize many words. It was hypothesized that concrete poetry could help improve receptive and expressive oral vocabulary, which in turn increased word recognition.

Introduction

What is a Word?

Words express meanings that often require, if not imply, their association with other words. Knowing a word or vocabulary requires word knowledge (e.g., affixes, word formation and word origins) and word meanings, knowing known as well as new words used in spoken language for listening and speaking (i.e., receptive and expressive oral vocabulary) as well as written language for reading and writing (i.e., productive and expressive written vocabulary). Vocabulary can also be presented as active vocabulary, i.e., words used in speaking and writing, as well as passive vocabulary, i.e., words used in listening and reading.

A word is the smallest linguistic unit that on its own can be meaningless unless it is placed in a certain context. That is to say its existence makes sense when being placed in speech and writing, with its meaning determined by the context in which it is found, such as a syntactic context (e.g., in a declarative sentence) or in a socio-cultural context (e.g., in a speech situation). For instance, what does the word *does* mean to you? When asked this question, most people give the same reply: *does* is a form of the verb “to do”. My response is they are partially correct. The word *does* can also refer to the plural form of *doe* – a female deer, or a female mammal like a hare or kangaroo.

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Linguistically speaking, a word is made up of a lexeme – an abstract unit – with or without several inflected forms. For instance, the word **give** belongs to the word class of verbs (more precisely, a lexical verb) and has the following inflected forms: **gives, given, giving, gave** and **gie** (a Scottish variant). Another word **gift** has the following inflected forms that belong to four different word classes: nouns: **gift, gifts, giftedness**; verbs: **gifted, gifting**; adjectives: **gifted**; and adverb: **giftedly**.

Constituents of a Word

A word is made up of three interactive elements: orthographic (letters), phonological (sounds) and semantic (meanings) – see Figure 1 (Chia, 1996a, 1996b, 1997a, 1998) below.

Figure 1: The three interactive elements of a word

The orthographic element can be further divided into two sub-elements: logographic elements (i.e., letter shapes and sequencing), and spelling rules and conventions. For instance, a word like **cat** is written **c-a-t** in the following sequence with **c** at the beginning, **a** in the middle and **t** at the end, and is made up of three letters (orthographic element) that shape as **c, a** and **t** forming its word shape **c a t**. It is spelled in the pattern of consonant-vowel-consonant (CVC), with each letter having its own letter name and letter sound. The letter **c** in **cat** is pronounced /k/, while **a** is pronounced /æ/ and **t** is pronounced as /t/ (phonological element). The word **cat** can also be heard as having one syllable. It has the onset **c** and the rhyme **at**. When this onset is substituted with other letters such as **b** as in **bat**, or **f** as in **fat**, the meaning of the word is changed (semantic element). Also, the word **cat** can mean different things in different contexts. For instance, the word **cat** in the following sentence:

That **cat** caught a mouse last night.

refers to a feline, while the word **cat** in another sentence such as:

The traitor let the **cat** out of the bag and betrayed his comrades to the enemy.
means 'to tell a secret.

Before a child can read, he or she needs to develop the concept of word, i.e., the ability to relate words in the head to words on the page or spoken during a conversation. It is crucial therefore for teachers to understand and know words, their meanings and usage, in order to teach children to read and use them effectively.

Literature Review

Process of Word Decoding

In decoding a word such as *cat*, it involves more than just the interaction of its three constituent elements mentioned above. Word decoding (see Figure 2) can be an auditory-sequential or visual-sequential process involving the following four stages: (1) word perception, (2) word analysis, (3) word meaning, and (4) word sense. Each of the four stages is briefly described below.

Figure 2: Process of word decoding

Stage 1:

Word perception takes place during the initial process of word decoding (i.e., reading and/or listening) in the mind of a reader/listener involving visual-sequential and/or auditory-sequential identification of the target word and some degree of meaning (Chia, 1997a). Harris and Hodges (1995) have defined it as the process of understanding the appropriate meaning of a word following its identification (for unfamiliar or new words seen in print or heard) or recognition (for words previously met in print or heard) (Harris & Hodges, 1995). According to Tinker (1965), the visual-sequential and/or auditory-sequential perception of words depends upon the meanings that are present in the identification and recognition of the words. After the word perception, comes the next process of word analysis.

Stage 2:

The three sub-processes of word analysis that happen in this stage are word discrimination, word identification and word recognition. According to Chia (1998), word analysis is the process of

analyzing a word in terms of its constituent parts: phonological, orthographic and semantic elements. It involves the process of noting differences in words, especially in their auditory-sequential (phonological) differences or visual-sequential (orthographic) outlines in terms of overall word shape or configuration. For example, the word **lamp** looks and sounds different from **lamb** and **lame**. This is known as word discrimination, which also involves both letter discrimination and letter sequencing (e.g., **there**, **three** and **their**). It is also used to make a sharp distinction between the process of *identifying* of an unknown word and the process of *recognizing* a word previously met (Durkin, 1993; Tinker, 1965). The former is known as word identification; the latter, word recognition. Both are two essential interacting cognitive processes that take place in this second stage of word decoding. However, only one of them can happen at any one time during the process of word decoding (Chia, 1997a; 1998).

If a word is new or unknown, word identification takes place. According to Harris and Hodges (1995), word identification is “the process of determining the pronunciation and some degree of meaning of an unknown word” (p.282). That means when the listener/reader is dealing with an unknown or new word, he/she may attempt to do a phonetic analysis of it, i.e., segmenting the unfamiliar word into its constituent phonemes and then pronouncing them as he/she blends them together as a word in its entirety. Also known as recoding, it is an alternative route that a child with dyslexia would resort to when he/she tries to decipher words (Chia, 2007). According to Manzo and Manzo (1994), phonetic analysis involves the reader/listener’s application of letter-to-sound relationships until a hypothesis can be made as to what the word probably is. The hypothesis is then tested against the context in which the word is used. A key component of phonetic analysis is the “distinguishing of boundaries of linguistic elements within the sound stream” (Clark, 1988:8), commonly known as phonemic awareness and phonemic segmentation. Other word identification skills include the following three types: (1) word analytical skills, e.g., phonic analysis and structural analysis; (2) using clues to guess a word, e.g., context clues, configuration clues, picture clues; and (3) dictionary skills.

On the other hand, word recognition involves a word previously met in print or writing. It is a quick and easy identification of the form, pronunciation, and appropriate meaning of a word encountered before. Manzo and Manzo (1994) define word recognition as a reader’s attempt to identify a word rapidly, with little attention to letter-to-sound relationships. This process relies heavily on eidetic imagery, that is, the ability to hold an image in the short-term memory while physically moving past it to other words or images in the working memory, to test to see if the word should be called one thing or another. For instance, is this word **there** or **three**? In word recognition, the reader depends on two additional aids: the most distinguishing features of the word (Gibson & Levin, 1975) and the context in which it is used (Pereira, 1991). Every word has special distinguishing features, including its configuration, or shape (Marchbanks & Levin, 1965). The word recognition process is especially crucial in the learning of phonetically irregular words that are used frequently in everyday speech and writing (Manso & Manzo, 1994).

In addition, both processes of word identification and word recognition also involve letter sequencing in a given word. For instance, the word **cat** is read as it is and spelled as **c-a-t** and is not read as **tac** or **act** and/or spelled as **t-a-c** and **a-c-t**.

Stage 3:

Word meaning is another important element in word knowledge. When a word is identified or recognized, its meaning is then established. Harris and Hodges (1995) define word meaning as “the concept of concepts associated with a spoken (auditory) or written (visual) word” (p.282). In word meaning, thought and speech are united into a verbal thought (Vygotsky, 1962) which is essential for our cognitive understanding of words.

A word meaning can be denotative or connotative. It can also be literal or figurative. This depends very much on how it is being used in a given context. This brings us to the next stage that is concerned with word sense.

Stage 4:

Word meaning is meaningless until it makes sense within a given context, which can be either a conversation or printed text. For instance, the word **cat** may have its meaning but it does not make any sense until it is placed in a given context as in the following two examples:

- (1) The **cat** pounced on the frightened mouse and ate it up.
- (2) Don't you let the **cat** out of its bag or we'll all be killed.

Notice that the **cat** in the first sentence has a different meaning from that in the second. The former is a feline; the latter, a secret.

Moreover, a word meaning is determined by its word order – a sequential arrangement of the target word in a phrase, clause or sentence. For instance, the **boy** in the following sentence is the actor of the action *munching*:

The **boy** is munching an apple.

He is different from the other **boy** – being the victim/receiver of the action, i.e., the robber's threat – in this sentence:

The robber threatened to hurt the **boy** unless he surrendered his wallet.

The various research studies and theories (e.g., Chia, 1996a, 1997a, 1998; Ehri, 1991, 1994; Gillet & Temple, 1990) about the word decoding process have given us a clearer view of the different pathways children take to identify or recognize words: (1) by sight word reading, when a child retrieves information about the words stored in his/her long-term memory from previous experiences reading the words; (2) by letter-sound decoding, which involves the child sounding out the letters and blending them into a word; (3) by analogy when the child accesses memory information about the familiar sight words to read unknown words; and (4) by contextual guessing that involves the child using meaning-based cues in preceding text or in illustrations to predict what a word might be (Ehri, 1991, 1994; Gaskins et al., 1997).

Development of Word Learning

According to Ehri's (1991, 1994) studies, children seem to progress through four different levels of word learning: pre-alphabetic, partial alphabetic, full alphabetic and consolidated alphabetic. These four levels are briefly discussed below.

Level 1: Pre-alphabetic

Before a child develops his/her letter awareness knowledge, he/she reads words by sight through memorization of distinctive visual cues in or around the word. Ehri (1995) called this process of word decoding visual-cue reading.

Level 2: Partial alphabetic

When the child acquires some knowledge of letters and their names and/or sounds, he/she remembers how to read specific words by noticing how a few letters correspond to salient sounds in the word's pronunciation. Ehri (1995) called this process of word decoding phonetic-cue reading.

Level 3: Full alphabetic

The child fully analyzes the spellings of words by matching up all the letters to sounds in their pronunciations.

Level 4: Consolidated alphabetic

The child uses larger units to remember how to read sight words. In other words, the child finds it easier to read and remember multi-syllabic words as sight words by dealing with chunks of letters (e.g., understanding = under + stand + ing) than each individual letter (e.g., u-n-d-e-r-s-t-a-n-d-i-n-g).

From Ehri's developmental phase theory of word learning, an explanation has been offered as to why some children might be encountering problems in decoding unfamiliar words. These children have failed to progress beyond the two initial levels in their sight word reading, i.e., they are still relying heavily on visual-cue or phonetic-cue reading (Chia, 1996b; Gaskins et al., 1997).

Knowing and understanding the elements that constitute a word, the four-stage process of word decoding and the four-level development of word learning provide us a better knowledge base for the know-how in planning successful lessons to impart word knowledge to our students, especially the young preschool children, who are about to embark on their formal literacy education.

Problems in Word Recognition

There are four categories of word decoders: (1) those who can recognize words previously met and know how to identify new or unknown words, i.e., readers with good word decoding; (2) those who can recognize familiar words and/or words previously met, but unable to identify new or unknown words, i.e., readers with dyslexia; (3) those who cannot recognize familiar words and/or words previously met, but somehow mysteriously are able to identify new or unknown words, i.e., readers with acquired aphasia and agnosia; and (4) those who cannot recognize nor identify words whether they are previously met or new/unknown, i.e., readers with alexia or word blindness. A fifth group, not found in this classification, refers to the precocious word decoders who are unable to understand what they are reading. They are readers with hyperlexia which may co-exist with autism spectrum disorders. A sixth group, also not found in the

classification, concerns those with impoverished vocabulary, word-finding difficulties and problem in acquiring new words (Bishop, 2006; Cohen, 2002). They are known to have both receptive and expressive language difficulties, and the term *specific language impairment* has been used to describe their problem (see Chia & Poh, 2009).

There are many children who cannot recognize and read words by sight, even if they have been taught by sounds (i.e., through phonics). They are of normal intelligence and without any impaired vision and hearing. They can converse well and understand what is spoken to them, but they are unable to recognize words. Many of them may have devised coping strategies for learning words but these are not very reliable or efficient (Gaskins et al., 1997). Others may attempt to remember words based on their shapes or salient visual features (Chia, 1996b, 1996c). Yet there are still other children who may rely heavily on a few symbol-sound associations, often for the first and last letters of words which are also known as determining letters (Harris & Hodges, 1995; Gaskins et al., 1997). All these children are sometimes described as being word blind (Chia, 1998) or termed as having word-reading difficulty (Gaskins et al., 1997) different from dyslexia.

How to Help Children with Poor Word Recognition Ability

Generally, there are three different approaches to dealing with low or poor word recognition ability (Chia, 1998):

1. The developmental approach is based on the belief that children with poor word recognition ability may have slower brain development. It aims to simply intensify conventional methods of instruction (Chia, 1997b; Spafford & Grosser, 1996).
2. The remedial approach focuses on learning deficiencies of these children with poor word recognition ability (Chia, 1994; Gaskins et al., 1997).
3. The corrective approach emphasizes the assets and interests of the child with poor word recognition ability, and teaches him/her (e.g., words related to the theme of dinosaurs) (Chia, 1997b; McNinch, 1981; Rupley & Blair, 1987).

The author of this present study has taken the third approach to work with a group of ten young children with low oracy/literacy in English language using concrete poetry as the pedagogical strategy to improve the word recognition of these children.

Concrete Poetry

Since the Second World War, concrete poetry has become a notable movement and several British poets including Simon Cutts, Stuart Mills and Ian Hamilton Finlay have written successful concrete verses. Two good representative collections of such poetry are *An Anthology of Concrete Poetry* edited by E. Williams (1967) and *Concrete Poetry: An International Anthology* edited by S. Bann (1967).

Concrete poetry reduces a poet's concern for continuity and the entire linguistic texture of poetry to isolated and particular aspects of visual, phonetic or kinetic structure, abandoning the normal poetic form whose meaning is disclosed at or below the level of the single word (Ousby, 1988:212). Its main objective is to present each poem as a different shape. Hence, it is a matter of pictorial typography that results in "visual poetry". It may be on the page, or on glass, stone,

wood and other materials (Cuddon, 1979). It is extremely difficult to execute well but the technique lends itself to great subtlety, as Apollinaire (1918) demonstrated in *Calligrammes*.

Different accounts of concrete poetry have either stressed its novel and experimental nature, making links with structuralism and semiotics (Ousby, 1988), or else have claimed a long tradition stemming from older texts whose visual aspects contributed to their meaning, such as George Herbert's *The Altar* (1633) and Dylan Thomas's *Vision and Prayer* (1953).

The Literary Perspective

Though some hold the view that the moment of concrete poetry is already past, from the literary perspective, some deem it can most usefully be seen as an episode in the continuing assertion of an internationalist avant-garde that has sought to break with the past and establish formal structures reflecting the scale of alteration that technology has unleashed on the world (Chia, 1993; Ousby, 1988).

The Pedagogical Perspective

From the pedagogical perspective, concrete poetry offers teachers in both primary schools and preschools a stimulating technique to get their children interested in poetry. There are four main objectives for introducing concrete poetry to children: firstly, it serves to increase understanding of layouts of letters to form a meaningful word; secondly, it allows the meaning of a word to be expressed through the shape, size, and physical layout of its letters; thirdly, it enhances memory for word shapes so as to enable a child to write recognizable words; and lastly, concrete poetry provides the child with a channel for his/her creative expression (Chia, 1991).

When teaching concrete poetry, the emphasis has to be on the visual appearance of letters. There is a need to consider the following factors (Chia, 1991:21):

1. "the shape of each letter in a word;
2. the size of each letter in the word; and
3. the physical layout of all the letters sequenced to make the word."

The physical design of a concrete poem puts its form ahead of its content. However, this is not an attempt to imply that that is the proper sequence of things (Chia, 1993). Indeed, most poets would argue that content (that is, feeling, idea and image) should come first, followed by its appropriate form. On the other hand, well-known English poets such as William Shakespeare have embraced both content and form in writing poems. In writing his comedies and tragedies, Shakespeare has worked from content to form, yet he writes over a hundred poems within a set form – the sonnet. Poets like George Herbert and Dylan Thomas have written their poems in which the physical layout is more important to them.

Likewise, children in preschools and primary schools can be turned on by a form, especially if it is a concrete poem. The concrete poems "do not have a line, meter, rhyme, rhythm, stanza or even title" (Chia, 1993:42). The poem consists of a word whose letters act out its meaning (Chia, 1988). There are many ways of teaching concrete poetry to children, but the aim is always to bring in the fun of creating concrete poems to them.

Teaching Concrete Poetry to Children with Special Needs

Concrete poetry is taught as a form of creative writing in mainstream schools (Chia, 1991, 1993, 1994, 1996c). The author has been unable to find any studies, other than his (see Chia, 1994, 1996b, 2006), on teaching concrete poetry to children with special needs. Chia (1995, 1996b) used concrete poetry to teach word recognition to children with hyperlexia. In addition, Chia (2006) and Chia et al. (in press) have also used concrete poetry to teach reading comprehension to children with Asperger's syndrome. This technique differs slightly from the stimulus shaping techniques that were developed in the 1970s to teach sight-word reading to children with mental retardation (see Duker, Didden, & Sigafos, 2004, for a review of several such studies).

The Study

Aim

The main purpose of this study was to determine the effectiveness of concrete poetry as a strategy to improve the word recognition of ten K-2 Chinese children with low oracy/literacy in English language.

Research Design

This quasi-experimental study used a single-group pre-test/post-test research design to investigate the effectiveness of concrete poetry as a strategy to improve the word recognition of the study subjects, observed at two time points, one before treatment and one after treatment. Two standardized tests were administered as pre- and post-tests. Changes in the outcome of interest (i.e., performance in word recognition measured by the standardized tests) are presumed to be the result of the treatment. No control or comparison group in employed. One reason is that the author was unable to find parents who would agree to put their children in a control group without any treatment. Taking into consideration the time constraints, the author felt that as an exploratory study it was a cost-effective way to discern if a potential treatment was worthy of further investigation in the future.

Single-group pre-test/post-test design meant that subjects of the study group were compared with themselves instead of to a control or nonequivalent comparison group. Data on the variable of interest (i.e., word recognition) were collected from standardized tests administered on the study group prior to the treatment, and after the treatment. The difference in test results is interpreted as the change resulting from the treatment. This is a reasonable way to achieve the goal of an experiment in the sense that all possible time-invariant factors associated with the study subjects are controlled. However, this design does not control for time-varying factors that may be coincidental with the study time frame (Kerlinger and Lee 2000).

The author acknowledges that it was difficult to assess the validity of this study as it did not include any control or comparison group. Hence, it is difficult to assess the significance of an observed change in the subjects. Any change could be due to historical changes unrelated to the treatment or to events that possibly occurred as a result of the experimenter's treatment, an artifact of testing and maturation of the subjects are amongst the many such threats to internal validity.

However, in order to ensure that the results of this study were reliable and valid, two actions were taken. First, the author introduced five selection criteria for potential subjects before they

were chosen to be involved in this study in order to keep the sample as homogeneous as possible. Second, the author used the Pearson's r correlation coefficient as an estimate of validity and reliability.

Participating Subjects

Initially, 32 interested parents, who came to know about this study by word of mouth, approached the author to express their interest in allowing their preschool children to participate in the study. However, not all met the following selection criteria as set by the author below:

1. The child must have normal intelligence. The author administered the Test of Nonverbal Intelligence-Third Edition (TONI-3) (Brown, Sherbenou, & Johnsen, 1997), which measures an individual's ability of abstract or figural problem-solving, for anyone ranging in ages from 6 years 0 months through 89 years 11 months. It was used to rule out any mentally challenged or developmentally delayed subjects, in case there was any, who had volunteered to participate in this study.

Two reasons why the TONI-3 was chosen for administration in this study are as follow: Firstly, its nonverbal or language-free format makes it ideal for evaluating the subjects, who spoke, read and/or write little English and displayed a lack of adequate exposure to the English language. It would have been otherwise difficult to assess these subjects with any degree of confidence or precision (Pierangelo & Giuliani, 2006) and, especially, without being socio-culturally biased. Secondly, the TONI-3 meets the highest psychometric standards for norms, reliability, and validity, and with a twenty-year body of reliability (Pierangelo & Giuliani, 2006). According to Brown, Sherbenou, and Johnsen, (2002), the reliability of the TONI-3 Form A using Cronbach's (1951) coefficient alpha for subjects between 6 years and 14 years old is in the range between .89 and .93, and a standard error of measurement ranging from .85 to 2.02. In addition, the reliability coefficients of TONI-3 Form A only are as follow: content reliability is .93; time sampling is .91; scorer difference is .99; and an average reliability coefficient of .96. Hence, the test has a high degree of reliability.

2. The chronological age of a subject must be between 6 years 0 months and 6 years 11 months of age. This age range was chosen because the lowest chronological age which allows the TONI-3 to be administered is 6 years 0 months.
3. As the study was targeted at K-2 children, the potential subject must be a preschooler currently attending a pre-school, kindergarten or childcare centre. Two preschool children, whose parents expressed interest to participate in this study, had to be excluded as they were home-schooled, and lacked the exposure in the typical learning context of a preschool.
4. The subject must come from a middle-income family with Mandarin-speaking home background. This exclusion criterion might seem racist at first but the author aimed to keep the sample as homogeneous as possible. Another reason is that subjects from different races learn English differently and face a different set of second language learning difficulties because of the interference of their mother tongues.

5. The subject must be identified by his/her form teacher to have low oracy or literacy in English language. The author administered the Word Finding Vocabulary Test-4th Edition (WFVT-4) (Renfrew, 1997), which is a subtest of the Renfrew Language Scales-Fourth Edition (RLS-4) (Renfrew, 1997), to assess the subject's spoken vocabulary (Fisher & Glenister, 1992) in terms of his/her ability to put a name to a picture shown. There are a total of 50 pictures arranged in order of difficulty for language-normal children, ranging from 3 years 6 months through 8 years 5 months. One reason why the WFVT-4 was administered on the ten subjects in this study is that rapid naming of pictures can be a useful indicator of general naming ability. According to Fisher and Glenister (1992), "naming difficulties may be apparent in the connected, conversational language of aphasic adults and of children who have language disorders. Such difficulty may be described in terms of the accuracy of the match between what was to be named and what was actually said. The presence of naming difficulties may also be indicated by unusually slow rates of word retrieval marked by inappropriate pauses in conversation" (p.1). A second reason is that picture naming can indicate an individual's word knowledge.

From among them, only ten were found to be suitable participants for the study. These ten subjects were all K-2 Chinese children (five boys and five girls) aged between 6 years 0 months and 6 years 11 months, coming from Mandarin-speaking middle-income families. The fathers of all the ten subjects are the sole bread-winners while the mothers except one (who was working as a clerical officer during the time of this study) are home-makers.

Table 1 shows the chronological ages (CA) of the subjects and the type of early childhood institution each subject came from.

Table 1: Subjects' Chronological Ages and Type of Early Childhood Institution attended

Subject Code/Gender	Chronological Age	Type of Early Childhood Institution
S1/M	6 years 3 months	Church kindergarten
S2/M	6 years 4 months	Montessori schoolhouse
S3/F	6 years 6 months	Childcare centre
S4/M	6 years 6 months	Childcare centre
S5/M	6 years 7 months	Childcare centre
S6/F	6 years 8 months	Church kindergarten
S7/F	6 years 8 months	Montessori schoolhouse
S8/F	6 years 9 months	Church kindergarten
S9/M	6 years 9 months	Church kindergarten
S10/F	6 years 10 months	Church kindergarten
Mean (Pre-test)	6 years 7 months	
Mean (Post-test)	7 years 1 month	

The mean chronological age (CA) of the ten subjects was 6 years 7 months (or 79 months) at the beginning of the study; 7 years 1 month (or 85 months) at the end of the study after a six-month treatment.

Table 2 shows the results of TONI-3 which suggest that the nonverbal intelligence (NVIQ) of eight subjects (S2/M, S3/F, S4/M, S5/M, S6/F, S8/F and S9/M) were within the average range (NVIQ between 90 and 110), while the NIIQs of two other subjects (S1/M and S10/F) were above average NVIQ (between 111 and 120). According to Exkorn (2003), any examinee with an NVIQ of 90 and above based on the administration of TONI-3 is unlikely to have mental retardation even if his/her speech is poor or in the case of a nonverbal child with autism spectrum disorder.

Table 2: Nonverbal IQs of Subjects (based on TONI-3 Form A only)

Subjects	Nonverbal IQ	Description
S1/M	112	Above Average
S2/M	105	Average
S3/F	96	Average
S4/M	93	Average
S5/M	92	Average
S6/F	103	Average
S7/F	104	Average
S8/F	115	Above Average
S9/M	98	Average
S10/F	117	Above Average

Key: S = Subject; M = Male; F = Female

Table 3 shows the results of WFVT-4 based on the raw scores and the equivalent vocabulary ages of the ten subjects. The group's mean raw score was 26 and six out of the ten subjects, i.e., S2/M, S6/F, S7/F, S8/F, S9/M and S10/F, met the cut-off. The other four, i.e., S1/M, S3/F, S4/M and S5/M, fell short of the group mean. However, when the raw scores were examined using the WFVT-4 norms, the results of all the ten subjects were far below the normative mean (between 35.4 and 37.5). In fact, all of them scored even below the lowest of the middle 50 per cent of their respective ranges of scores, i.e., 31-39 for subjects S1/M and S2/M, 35-41 for subjects S4/M, S5/M and S9/M, and 35-40 for subjects S3/F, S6/F, S7/F, S8/F and S10/F (at the beginning of the study three weeks before treatment). According to Renfrew (1997), failure in this test suggested that "this may be due to low intelligence, environmental deprivation, bilingual home background, emotional blocking, and/or specific word finding difficulty" (p.11).

Results obtained in the TONI-3 ruled out low intelligence. The author's informal interviews with the parents and observations of the subjects ruled out environmental deprivation and emotional blocking. All the ten subjects were from middle-income families with Mandarin-speaking home background. The only possible causes for their poor performance in WFVT-4 were bilingual home background, and/or specific word finding difficulty. For the first factor, it was a probable cause since all the subjects spoke mainly Mandarin at home and used only a smattering of English in their preschool, kindergarten or childcare centre when conversing with their teachers. As a result, it would not be surprising if their limited exposure to English or non-English

background might have caused them to display some specific word finding difficulty which should not be confused or mistaken to be some form of language disorder.

Table 3: Performance in Word Finding Vocabulary/Naming Ability

Subjects	RS	VA Equivalent	WFVT-4 Norms			
			Means	Medians	Middle 50% of range of scores	SD
S1/M	22	3y 10m-11m	35.4	34	31-39	6.49
S2/M	27	4y 6m	35.4	34	31-39	6.49
S3/F	25	4y 3m	37.5	37	35-40	4.07
S4/M	23	4y 0m	37.0	37	35-41	5.46
S5/M	24	4y 1m-2m	37.0	37	35-41	5.46
S6/F	28	4y 7m-8m	37.5	37	35-40	4.07
S7/F	29	4y 9m-10m	37.5	37	35-40	4.07
S8/F	27	4y 6m	37.5	37	35-40	4.07
S9/M	26	4y 4m-5m	37.0	37	35-41	5.46
S10/F	29	4y 9m	37.5	37	35-40	4.07
Mean	26	4y 4m				
SD	2.49					

Key: S = Subject; M = Male; F = Female; RS = Raw Score; VA = Vocabulary Age; y = years; m = months; SD = Standard Deviation

Instrumentation

Two standardized tests were administered as pre-/post-tests before and after treatment. They are the Comprehensive Receptive and Expressive Vocabulary Test-Second Edition (CREVT-2) (Wallace & Hammill, 2002), and the Word Recognition and Phonic Skills Test-Second Edition (WRaPS-2) (Moseley, 2003).

1. Comprehensive Receptive and Expressive Vocabulary Test-Second Edition (CREVT-2) (Wallace & Hammill, 2002)

The CREVT-2 has two subtests that measure both receptive and expressive oral vocabulary (word knowledge and meaning) for anyone ranging in ages from 4 years 0 months through 89 years 11 months. It was used in this study to identify if the subjects were significantly below their peers in oral vocabulary proficiency and also to note the discrepancies between receptive and expressive oral vocabulary.

The CREVT-2 was chosen for pre-/post-test administration in this study because oral vocabulary is probably the most important indicator of general learning ability that is needed in order to perform well in school (Harris & Sipay, 1990). Also, oral vocabulary consists of word knowledge and word meaning which are essential to word recognition/identification and word learning – the precursor to emergent literacy in young children.

The CREVT-2's overall reliability exceeds .90 and 14 (58 per cent) of its 24 coefficients meet or exceed the more rigorous standard of .95, which is considered the desirable standard (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994). The reliability of the CREVT-2 Form A for receptive oral

vocabulary has a coefficient alpha (Cronbach, 1951) of .93; a test-retest reliability of .96; and a reliability coefficient for scorer difference of .99. The reliability of the CREVT-2 Form B for receptive oral vocabulary has a coefficient alpha of .93; a test-retest reliability of .98; and a reliability coefficient for scorer difference of .99. The reliability coefficient for alternate form (immediate) between Forms A and B is .94 while that for alternate form (delayed) between Forms A and B is .95.

The reliability of the CREVT-2 Form A for expressive oral vocabulary has a coefficient alpha (Cronbach, 1951) of .89; a test-retest reliability of .94; and that of scorer difference is .99. Similarly, the reliability of the CREVT-2 Form B for expressive oral vocabulary has a coefficient alpha of .89 but a slightly lower test-retest reliability of .93 as well as lower reliability coefficient for scorer difference of .97. The reliability coefficient of alternate form (immediate) between Forms A and B is .88 while that of alternate form (delayed) between Forms A and B is .91.

Finally, the reliability of the CREVT-2 Form A for general oral vocabulary has the same coefficient alpha (Cronbach, 1951) of .95 for both Forms A and B, same test-retest reliability of .96 and same reliability for scorer difference of .99. The reliability coefficient of alternate form (immediate) between Forms A and B is .94 while that of alternate form (delayed) is .95.

2. *Word Recognition and Phonic Skills Test-Second Edition (WRaPS-2) (Moseley, 2003)*

The WRaPS-2 can be group or individually administered and is designed to measure a child's word recognition ability based on his/her word recognition standardized score expressed in terms of

- (a) word recognition age equivalent;
- (b) ten stages of word recognition; and
- (c) the length of a word that is recognized about 80 per cent of the time (Moseley, 2003).

The WRaPS-2 was chosen for pre-/post-test administration in this study because word recognition is "an important measure of children's developing knowledge about written language as well as the major route to meaning, a fundamental pre-requisite for comprehension" (Moseley, 2003:5). A second reason is that the WRaPS-2 can provide a diagnostic profile of strengths and weaknesses in phonic skills which shows whether the child is sensitive to the appropriate range of cues at a given level of development.

The WRaPS-2 was standardized in 2002-3 on 4775 pupils in 111 schools, after extensive piloting to ensure good item discrimination and equivalence between Forms A and B. The internal consistency reliability of the test is very high, the overall Cronbach's (1951) alpha value being .97 in both Forms A and B. Even in the Reception year, where children are most likely to resort to guessing, the alpha values are .86 and .84. In addition, a word length score (WLS) was calculated to represent the length of word correctly recognized at least 80 per cent of the time. This too proves to be a reliable index, with an alpha value of .87. Its validity as a measure of progress in word recognition is confirmed because it is strongly correlated with performance on each test ($r = .89$ with Form A raw score and $.93$ with Form B).

Setting/Schedule

This study was carried out at the Learning Disabilities Centre over a period of six months from March to August 2008. The subjects came to the centre twice a week on Wednesday and Friday evenings from 7.30pm to 8.30pm (i.e., a one-hour session).

Treatment

The author taught concrete poetry to the ten subjects at three different levels over six months. Each level is briefly described below:

Level 1 (Elementary): This first level was taught in March and April. At this level, shapes of things (e.g., cup, bowl, house, pen, chair) and animals (e.g., cat, dog, bird, butterfly, snake) were outlined on a piece of construction paper. They were cut out. The author wrote the name of the thing or animal on the cut-out lightly in pencil so that it could be easily erased later. For example, if it is a cut-out of an arrow, the word **ARROW** or **arrow** is written in pencil on the cut-out. The child can identify the object quickly and easily (see Illustration 1 below):

Illustration 1: A Concrete Poem of an Arrow

Next, the subjects would be told or shown how the shape of each letter in the given word could fit into the cut-out. A concrete poem would eventually take form (see Illustration 1 above). This is the best way to introduce concrete poetry to those who are new to it.

Level 2 (Intermediate): This second level was taught in May and June. At this level, the subjects were given a list of interesting content words like nouns, adjectives and verbs (e.g., eye, tall, look), and be allowed or encouraged to create their own original forms from these words. Illustration 2 below shows some examples of these concrete poems:

Illustration 2: Concrete Poems of eye, tall and look

Level 3 (Advanced): This third and last level was taught in July and August. At this advanced level, the subjects were encouraged to come up with their very own words and create their original concrete poems. They were also being introduced some other activities involving discussion over some given concrete poems, either among the subjects themselves (pair or group work) or with the author who prompted them with questions. Below are two examples of concrete poems used for discussion with the subjects (see Illustrations 3 and 4):

Illustration 3: A Concrete Poem for Discussion

1NE .
2WO ..
3HREE ...
4OUR
5IVE

A question that can be asked: “Can you think of other ways to make a numbers poem?”

Illustration 4: Another Concrete Poem for Discussion

STRETCH
 S T R E T C H
 S T R E T C H
 S T R E T C H
 S T R E T C H
 S T R E T C H
 S T R E T C H
 S T R E T C H

A question that can be asked: “This concrete poem makes us feel visually as if the word is being stretched physically to its limits. Can you come up with another concrete poem that can make one feels visually heavy, light, hot, cold, etc.?”

Results and Discussion

As mentioned earlier, the aim of this study was to determine the effectiveness of concrete poetry as a strategy to improve the word recognition of K-2 Chinese children with low oracy/literacy in English language.

CREVT-2 Results

Table 4 shows the results of CREVT-2 based on the first of the two oral vocabulary subtests, i.e., the test of receptive oral vocabulary, which was administered two days before the treatment began. It “measures the ability of the subject to understand the meaning of individual words when spoken in isolation” (Wallace & Hammill, 2002:29). The mean raw score for the Receptive Oral Vocabulary at pre-test (Form A) was 17.5 (SD = 1.78; $\sigma^2 = 3.17$) with a mean equivalent receptive oral vocabulary (ROV) age of 5 years 4 months (SD = 3.41; $\sigma^2 = 11.6$) below the mean CA (at pre-test phase) of 6 years 7 months (a difference of 1 year 3 months apart), while the mean raw score at post-test (Form B) was 24.9 (SD = 2.77; $\sigma^2 = 7.66$) with a mean equivalent ROV age of 6 years 7 months (SD = 5.87; $\sigma^2 = 34.4$) below the mean CA (at post-test) of 7 years 1 month (a difference of 0 year 6 months apart). This finding suggests the subjects as a group were catching up and closing up the gap between their mean chronological age and mean ROV age from a difference of 15 months apart at pre-test to 6 months apart at post-test.

The correlation coefficient r was computed to determine the strength of the linear association between the subjects’ pre-test and post-test raw scores, their ROV ages and standard scores (SS). It was also to investigate whether there was a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores and whether the subjects improved as a result of the treatment. The results indicated that there was a definite but small relationship between the pre-test and post-test raw scores, i.e., a low correlation, $r = .28$. A similar low correlation was also noted in their ROV ages, $r = .26$. However, there was a moderate correlation or substantial relationship between the pre-test and post-test standard scores for the ROV, $r = .48$. Although the standard scores had a slightly better correlation coefficient than the raw scores and ROV ages to show that the standard scores were better predictors of whether concrete poetry did help improve the subjects’ receptive oral vocabulary, it is not considered high enough to be used as a definite predictor (F. William, 1968).

Table 4: Performance in Receptive Oral Vocabulary (ROV)

Subjects	Form A (Pre-Test)				Form B (Post-Test)			
	RS	ROV Age (in months)	SS	Description	RS	ROV Age (in months)	SS	Description
S1/M	14	57	84	Below Ave	27	84	102	Ave
S2/M	19	66	93	Ave	26	81	100	Ave
S3/F	17	63	85	Below Ave	24	78	92	Ave
S4/M	16	60	83	Below Ave	20	69	86	Below Ave
S5/M	17	63	85	Below Ave	22	72	89	Below Ave
S6/F	20	69	90	Ave	26	81	96	Ave
S7/F	19	66	88	Below Ave	24	78	92	Ave
S8/F	17	63	85	Below Ave	24	78	92	Ave
S9/M	17	63	85	Below Ave	26	81	96	Ave
S10/F	19	66	88	Below Ave	30	90	102	Ave
Mean	17.5	63.6	86.6	Below Ave	24.9	79.2	94.7	Ave
SD	1.78	3.41	3.10		2.77	5.87	5.46	
Variance (σ^2)	3.17	11.6	9.60		7.66	34.4	29.79	

Key: S = Subject; M = Male; F = Female; SD = Standard Deviation; RS = Raw Score; ROV = Receptive Oral Vocabulary; SS = Standard Score

From Table 4, only two subjects S2/M and S6/F managed to attain average standard scores of 93 and 90 respectively for the receptive oral vocabulary at pre-test. All the others had below average standard scores at pre-test with a mean standard score of 86.6 (in the below average range). At the post-test, all except S4/M and S5/M attained an average standard score in the receptive oral vocabulary in the range between 92 and 102 with a mean standard score of 94.7 (SD = 5.46; $\sigma^2 = 29.79$) for the group. Standard scores for receptive oral vocabulary of the two subjects S4/M and S5/M were in the below average range for both pre-test (83 and 85 respectively) and post-test (86 and 89 respectively).

As a group, there was an increase in the mean standard score from 86.6 (below average) at pre-test to 94.7 (average) at post-test (an increase by 8.1 points).

Table 5 shows the results of CREVT-2 based on the second oral vocabulary subtest, i.e., the test of expressive oral vocabulary, which was administered two days before the treatment began. It “measures the ability of the subject’s ability to define stimulus words precisely. Because the format of this subtest requires people to say specifically what a word means, its results yield much more definitive information about their knowledge of word meanings than does the receptive vocabulary subtest” (Wallace & Hammill, 2002:29). The mean raw score at pre-test (Form A) was 5.1 (SD = 0.99; $\sigma^2 = 0.99$) with a mean equivalent expressive oral vocabulary (EOV) age of 5 years 1 month (SD = 6.33; $\sigma^2 = 40.1$) below the mean CA (at pre-test) of 6 years 7 months (a difference of 1 year 6 months apart), while the mean raw score at post-test

(Form B) was 7.2 (SD = 0.79; $\sigma^2 = 0.62$) with a mean equivalent EOV age of 6 years 1 month (SD = 4.73; $\sigma^2 = 22.4$) below the mean CA (at post-test) of 7 years 1 month (a difference of 1 year 0 month apart). This finding suggests the subjects as a group were catching up and closing up the gap between their mean chronological age and mean EOV age from a difference of 18 months apart at pre-test to 12 months apart at post-test.

Table 5: Performance in Expressive Oral Vocabulary (EOV)

Subjects	Form A (Pre-Test)				Form B (Post-Test)			
	RS	EOV Age (in months)	SS	Description	RS	EOV Age (in months)	SS	Description
S1/M	5	60	90	Ave	8	78	99	Ave
S2/M	5	60	90	Ave	7	72	95	Ave
S3/F	6	66	91	Ave	6	66	91	Ave
S4/M	3	48	79	Poor	6	66	87	Below Ave
S5/M	4	54	83	Below Ave	7	72	87	Below Ave
S6/F	6	66	91	Ave	8	78	95	Ave
S7/F	5	60	87	Below Ave	7	72	91	Ave
S8/F	5	60	87	Below Ave	8	78	95	Ave
S9/M	6	66	91	Ave	7	72	91	Ave
S10/F	6	69	91	Ave	8	78	95	Ave
Mean	5.1	60.9	88	Below Ave	7.2	73.2	92.6	Ave
SD	0.99	6.33	4.11		0.79	4.73	3.86	
Variance (σ^2)	0.99	40.1	16.89		0.62	22.4	14.93	

Key: S = Subject; M = Male; F = Female; SD = Standard Deviation; RS = Raw Score; EOV = Expressive Oral Vocabulary; SS = Standard Score

As mentioned earlier, the correlation coefficient r was computed to investigate whether there was a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores (Odom & Morow, 2006) and whether the subjects improved as a result of the treatment in terms of their pre-test and post-test raw scores, EVO ages and standard scores (SS). The results indicated that there was a definite but small relationship between the pre-test and post-test raw scores, i.e., a low correlation, $r = .40$. A moderate correlation was also noted in their EOV ages, $r = .42$. Similarly, there was a higher moderate correlation or substantial relationship between the pre-test and post-test standard scores for the EOV, $r = .70$. According to Heffner (2004) and F. Williams (1968), a correlation of .70 and above is almost always significant. These findings suggest that standard scores had a better correlation coefficient than the raw scores and EOV ages and hence, were better predictors to show that concrete poetry did help improve the subjects' expressive oral vocabulary.

From Table 5, only one subject S3/F's standard score of 91 for the expressive oral vocabulary remained the same for both pre-test and post-test. Another subject S4/M had poor standard score while the standard scores of three others, i.e., S5/M, S7/F and S8/F, were in the below average range. The mean standard score for the group at pre-test was 88 (below average). At the post-test, all except S4/M and S5/M attained an average standard score in the expressive oral

vocabulary in the range between 91 and 99 with a mean standard score of 92.6 ($SD = 3.87$; $\sigma^2 = 14.93$) for the group. Standard scores for expressive oral vocabulary of the subject S5/M at pre-test and post-test were in the below average range of 83 and 87 respectively. As for the subject S4/M, his standard score of 79 (poor) at pre-test moved up to 87 (below average) at post-test.

As a group, there was an increase in the mean standard score from 88 (below average) at pre-test to 92.6 (average) at post-test (a small increase by 4.6 points).

It is interesting to note that when the pre-test (Form A) results of both subtests of CREVT-2 were compared at group level, ROV age of 5 years 4 months ($SD = 3.41$; $\sigma^2 = 11.6$) was slightly higher than the mean EOVS age of 5 years 1 month ($SD = 6.33$; $\sigma^2 = 40.1$). There was only a small difference of 3 months. Similarly, the mean standard score for ROV of 86.6 ($SD = 3.10$; $\sigma^2 = 9.6$) was 1.4 points higher than that of EOVS of 88 ($SD = 4.11$; $\sigma^2 = 16.89$) (see Table 6).

Table 6: A Comparison of CREVT-2 ROV & EOVS Subtest Results at Pre-Test

Subjects	ROV Age (in months)	EOVS Age (in months)	SS1 (ROV)	SS2 (EVO)	Difference between SS1 & SS2
S1/M	57	60	84	90	6
S2/M	66	60	93	90	3
S3/F	63	66	85	91	6
S4/M	60	48	83	79	4
S5/M	63	54	85	83	2
S6/F	69	66	90	91	1
S7/F	66	60	88	87	1
S8/F	63	60	85	87	2
S9/M	63	66	85	91	6
S10/F	66	69	88	91	3
Mean	63.6	60.9	86.6	88	3.4
SD	3.41	6.33	3.10	4.11	
Variance (σ^2)	11.6	40.1	9.6	16.89	

Key: M = Male; F = Female; ROV = Receptive Oral Vocabulary; EVO = Expressive Oral Vocabulary; SS = Standard Score; SD = Standard Deviation

In order to investigate whether there was a significant difference between the two subtest results in terms of the subjects' equivalent ages and standard scores between ROV and EOVS at the pre-test, a correlation coefficient r was computed. The results indicated that there was a definite but small relationship between the equivalent ages and standard scores between ROV and EOVS at pre-test, with the following respective low correlations, $r = .48$ for equivalent ages and $r = .46$ for the standard scores. Both correlation coefficient reliabilities, though may be considered significant (Heffner, 2004), were not high enough to merit using them as predictors to show the

consistency in the measurement (Odom & Morrow, 2006) of the effectiveness of concrete poetry as a strategy to improve word recognition between the ROV and EOV subtests at pre-test.

At individual subject's level, there was a slightly different picture to be seen. Five (i.e., S2/M, S4/M, S5/M, S7/F and S8/F) of the ten subjects scored higher on the ROV subtest than on the EOV subtest. According to the explanations given by Wallace and Hammill (2002), some of these subjects "could be naturally nonverbal or taciturn in their speech, some are learning English as a second language and therefore understand more words than they use properly in speech, some are affected by varying degrees of expressive dysphasia, some are shy around strangers such as examiners, some are unusually lucky guessers on the Receptive Oral Vocabulary subtest items" (p.30).

Unlike the other five subjects mentioned above and at the group level, the respective ROV ages of the other five subjects – S1/M, S3/F, S6/F, S9/M and S10/F – were lower than their respective EOV ages. There are fewer plausible reasons to explain why these subjects scored higher on the EOV subtest than on the ROV subtest. Presumably, according to Wallace and Hammill (2002),

"one must know the meanings of words before one can use the same words correctly in free discourse. This being a common presumption, one would therefore expect that instances where examinees score significantly higher on the Expressive Oral Vocabulary subtest than on Receptive Oral Vocabulary subtest would be relatively uncommon. Yet, such instances do occur. Perhaps, a few have undetected visual problems or find the pictures on the receptive subtest confusing. Although theoretically possible, receptive dysphasia is an unlikely explanation for this discrepancy due to the rareness of the disorder. More than likely, this particular discrepancy is the result of test or scorer error, situational error (distractions to the student or examiner, noise level, room temperature), or subject error (inattention, fatigue, low energy level, poor attitude, lack of motivation)" (p.30).

From the comparison of differences between the ROV and EOV standard scores at pre-test (Form A), there was a wide deviation of more than one standard deviation (in a range between 2 and 6 standard deviations) for most subjects except S6/F and S7/F. Moreover, the mean standard score difference between ROV and EOV at the group level was 3.4. However, the discrepancy between the ROV and EOV standard scores for each of the ten subjects reported in the findings here was below the 12-point criterion to be statistically significant ($p < .05$). For instance, consider the subject S1/M's standard score performance on the ROV and EOV subtests of 84 and 90, respectively (see Table 6). Although the standard score of ROV was 84 in the below average range and his standard score of EOV was 90 in the average range, as the difference between the scores did not reach the 12-point criterion, it was not possible to conclude that S1/M's ROV was significantly lower than his EOV. There must be a difference score of 12 points or greater to be statistically significant and at the .05 level of confidence (Wallace & Hammill, 2002).

In Table 7, when the post-test (Form B) results of both subtests of CREVT-2 were compared at group level, the mean ROV age of 6 years 7 months ($SD = 5.87$; $\sigma^2 = 34.4$) was slightly higher

than the mean EOVS age of 6 years 1 month ($SD = 4.73$; $\sigma^2 = 22.4$). There was only a small difference of 6 months. Similarly, the mean standard score for ROV of 94.7 ($SD = 5.46$; $\sigma^2 = 29.79$) was 2.1 points higher than that of EOVS of 92.6 ($SD = 3.86$; $\sigma^2 = 14.93$). Like in the pre-test, the discrepancy between the mean ROV and EOVS standard scores was 2.9, statistically insignificant for saying which oral vocabulary is weaker or stronger than the other.

Table 7: A Comparison of CREVT-2 ROV & EOVS Subtest Results at Post-Test

Subjects	ROV Age (in months)	EOVS Age (in months)	SS1 (ROV)	SS2 (EVO)	Difference between SS1 & SS2
S1/M	84	78	102	99	3
S2/M	81	72	100	95	5
S3/F	78	66	92	91	1
S4/M	69	66	86	87	1
S5/M	72	72	89	87	2
S6/F	81	78	96	95	1
S7/F	78	72	92	91	1
S8/F	78	78	92	95	3
S9/M	81	72	96	91	5
S10/F	90	78	102	95	7
Mean	79.2	73.2	94.7	92.6	2.9
SD	5.87	4.73	5.46	3.86	
Variance (σ^2)	34.4	22.4	29.79	14.93	

Key: M = Male; F = Female; ROV = Receptive Oral Vocabulary; EVO = Expressive Oral Vocabulary; SS = Standard Score; SD = Standard Deviation

In the post-test (Form B), most of the subjects except S4/M and S5/M scored in the average range of standard scores between 90 and 110. According to Wallace and Hammill (2002), “when both standard scores are 90 or above, one may conclude that the person is exhibiting an average or better grasp of the abilities measured on the CREVT-2” (p.30). However, on the other hand, if anyone has scored a balanced quotient below 90, this suggests the possibility or “some degree of mental retardation, language disorder, learning disability, or global dysphasia” (Wallace & Hammill, 2002:30) and in such instances, a thorough evaluation of linguistic cognitive ability would be strongly recommended and should include the administration of an appropriate test of nonverbal aptitude (e.g., TONI-3). In this study, all the ten subjects had undergone the TONI-3 administration and found to be in average and/or above average range of nonverbal intelligence. Hence, the subjects’ (especially S4/M and S5/M) poor performance in CREVT-2 could not be due to mental retardation, but other challenging issues such as, in this case, what their learning support teachers suspected them to have, the specific language impairment.

The correlation coefficient r was computed to determine if the difference between the subjects’ equivalent ages and standard scores between ROV and EOVS at post-test was significant and

whether the subjects showed an improvement. The results indicated that there was clearly a moderate correlation and hence, a substantial relationship between the equivalent ages at post-test, $r = .66$. As for the standard scores between ROV and EOJ at post-test, its correlation coefficient was high with a marked relationship between the two subtests, $r = .84$. The correlation coefficient reliability for comparing the ROV and EOJ standard scores were high enough to earn confidence to use them as a predictor to show the consistency in the measurement (Odom & Morrow, 2006) of the effectiveness of concrete poetry as a strategy to improve word recognition between the ROV and EOJ subtests at post-test.

At the individual subject's level, there were eight subjects, i.e., S1/M, S2/M, S3/F, S5/M, S6/F, S7/F, S9/M and S10/M, who scored slightly higher on the ROV subtest than on the EVO subtest. There was a change in the post-test group profile. Subjects S1/M, S3/F, S6/F, S9/M and S10/F were the new additions. Their previous standard scores on the EOJ subtest were higher than on the ROV subtest (between 1 and 6 points) though not significantly. The two original subjects S4/M and S8/F in pre-test group profile now scored slightly higher on the EOJ subtest than on the ROV subtest between 1 and 3 points difference. While it is difficult to explain the change, the discrepancy between ROV and EOJ standard scores for S4/M and S8/F was too small to be of any significance.

From these findings, it is interesting to note that all the ten subjects achieved between below-average and average standard scores in both ROV and EOJ subtests at post-test. Although the difference between the ROV and EOJ scores in this study was not large enough to be significant or clinically useful, the same could be said if the two subtest scores were statistically different. As Kaufman (1990) has pointed out, quite correctly, that one should not assume that the difference has to be large enough to be clinically useful. The use of statistical significance alone will tend to identify too many false positives. According to Reynolds (1985), for data to be clinically useful, the difference between the ROV and EOJ quotients must be 24 points or greater to show clinical usefulness.

Table 8 shows the results of the subjects' performance in the General Vocabulary Composite (GVC), which according to Wallace and Hammill (2002), is the best CREVT-2 measure of what is commonly known as vocabulary or word knowledge. The reason given by Wallace and Hammill (2002) is that "because it comprises information about the vocabulary ability that is derived from two testing formats (i.e., ROV and EOJ subtests) rather than just one" (p.28).

Those subjects (especially S1/M and S10/F) who scored well on this composite demonstrated the mastery of word meanings in spoken language, i.e., they could comprehend the meanings of words in other people's speech and use words properly in their own conversations. In other words, they would be considered to be verbally competent in oral language. This in turn would lead to higher performance in other verbal skills taught and used in school (e.g., reading and writing). Also, for these subjects, they would also score highly on a test of intelligence (or aptitude) as it normally measures oral and/or written vocabulary skills (Wallace & Hammill, 2002).

From Table 8, six subjects (i.e., S2/M, S3/F, S6/F, S7/F, S9/M and S10/F) scored a composite above the mean GVC of 84.8 ($SD = 3.82$; $\sigma^2 = 14.62$) at pre-test, but only four (i.e., S1/M, S2/M,

S6/F and S10/F) managed to do so at post-test, above the mean GVC of 92.4 (SD = 5.36; $\sigma^2 = 28.71$). Among those subjects who failed to score above the mean GVC at post-test but still attained a GVC in the average range of 90-110 were S7/F, S8/F and S9/M. Only two subjects S4/M and S5/M scored very poorly on the GVC as they scored 87 and 84, respectively, i.e., in the below average range of 80-89. The results indicated that there was clearly a moderate correlation and hence, a substantial relationship between the GVCs at pre-test and post-test, $r = .63$, as a predictor on the effectiveness of concrete poetry as a strategy to improve word recognition.

According to Wallace and Hammill (2002), low scores may suggest that the examinee could be “impaired intellectually, who do not speak or understand English well, who have dysphasia, who come from backgrounds that are lacking in sufficient vocabulary enrichment, or who are deaf or have other hearing impairments” (p.29). Without proper attention, these individuals are likely to fail in school. In this study, S4/M and S5/M were the two potential candidates to fit into this profile. As a result of their poor composites, it is important to relook into their ROV and EOVS subtest scores.

Table 8: Performance in General Vocabulary Composite

Subjects	Form A (Pre-Test)			Form B (Post-Test)		
	Sum of SS (ROV = EOVS)	GVC	Description	Sum of SS (ROV + EOVS)	GVC	Description
S1/M	174	84	Below Ave	201	101	Ave
S2/M	183	90	Ave	195	97	Ave
S3/F	176	86	Below Ave	179	87	Below Ave
S4/M	162	77	Poor	173	84	Below Ave
S5/M	168	81	Below Ave	180	88	Below Ave
S6/F	181	89	Below Ave	191	95	Ave
S7/F	175	85	Below Ave	183	90	Ave
S8/F	172	83	Below Ave	187	92	Ave
S9/M	176	86	Below Ave	187	92	Ave
S10/F	179	87	Below Ave	197	98	Ave
Mean		84.8			92.4	
SD		3.82			5.36	
Variance (σ^2)		14.62			28.71	

Key: S = Subject; M = Male; F = Female; Sum of SS = Sum of Standard Scores of Receptive Oral Vocabulary + Expressive Oral Vocabulary; GVC = General Vocabulary Composite

WRaPS-2 Results

WRaPS-2 was administered two days before the treatment began. Table 9 shows the results of WRaPS-2 based on: (1) word recognition age (in months); (2) word length score, which means that an examinee can recognize at least 80 per cent of words of a given length; and (3) the word recognition/phonics stages.

From Table 9, the results showed that there was a big improvement in the raw scores from pre-test to post-test. The mean raw score for the number of words the subjects could recognize was 15.4 (SD = 2.37; $\sigma^2 = 5.6$) at pre-test but raised up to 28.3 (SD = 7.67; $\sigma^2 = 58.9$) at post-test. There was a significant improvement in word recognition by 12.9 points. The word recognition (WR) age was 4 years 11 months (SD = 4.83; $\sigma^2 = 23.34$) at pre-test, but the WR age at post-test was 6 years 3 months (SD = 6.38; $\sigma^2 = 40.68$). There was a group improvement by 1 year 3 months in word recognition. From the results, a correlation coefficient was computed by comparing between their WR ages at pre-test and post-test with $r = .80$. According to F. Williams (1968), a coefficient of .80 and above is a good linear correlation and indicates that it is a good predictor of the subjects' performance in word recognition through concrete poetry.

Table 9: Performance in Word Recognition, Word Length Score & Word Recognition & Phonic Skills Developmental Stages

Subjects	Form A (Pre-Test)				Form B (Post-Test)			
	RS	WR Age (in months)	WLS	WRPS	RS	WR Age (in months)	WLS	WRPS
S1/M	<12	<54	-	1	24	72	2	4
S2/M	17	63	2	3	36	80	3	5
S3/F	15	60	-	2	24	72	2	4
S4/M	13	56	-	2	15	62	2	3
S5/M	14	58	-	2	20	68	2	3
S6/F	18	65	2	3	33	79	3	5
S7/F	16	62	-	2	34	79	3	5
S8/F	13	56	-	2	26	74	2	4
S9/M	17	63	2	3	32	78	3	5
S10/F	19	66	2	3	39	83	4	6
Mean	15.4	59.3			28.3	74.7		
SD	2.37	4.83			7.67	6.38		
Variance (σ^2)	5.6	23.34			58.9	40.68		

Key: S = Subject; M = Male; F = Female; RS = Raw Score; WR = Word Recognition; WLS = Word Length Score; WRPS = Word Recognition/Phonics Stage

Table 10 is a descriptive summary of the progression made by the ten subjects in word recognition and phonics as assessed by the WRaPS-2. The results have clearly shown that these subjects were becoming increasingly sensitive to the structure of spoken and written words. Everyone moved upward to higher developmental levels at post-test. Three subjects S1/M, S7/F and S10/F showed the biggest improvement when they moved up by three developmental levels;

five subjects S2/M, S3/F, S6/F, S8/F and S9/M improved by two developmental levels; and two subjects S4/M and S5/M made the least improvement, increasing by one developmental level. What each of these subjects achieved in word recognition and phonic skills at each stage is described briefly below:

Table 10: Performance in Word Recognition & Phonic Skills Developmental Stages

Form A (Pre-Test)		Form B (Post-Test)	
Subjects	WRPS	Subjects	WRPS
S1/M	1	-	1
S3/F, S4/M, S5/M, S7/F, S8/F	2	-	2
S2/M, S6/F, S9/M, S10/F	3	S4/M, S5/M	3
-	4	S1/M, S3/F, S8/F	4
-	5	S2/M, S6/F, S7/F, S9/M	5
-	6	S10/F	6

Key: S = Subject; M = Male; F = Female; WRPS = Word Recognition & Phonic Skills Developmental Stage

Stage 1:

At pre-test, only one subject S1/M was at this developmental level. According to Moseley (2003), “there is virtually no word recognition or letter knowledge” (p.25). At post-test, none of the subjects was at this stage. Subject S1/M improved significantly moving up from this level to Stage 4.

Stage 2:

At pre-test, five subjects (S3/F, S4/M, S5/M, S7/F and S8/F) came under this developmental level, where “a few initial letters are known” (Moseley, 2003:28). At post-test, none of the subjects was at this developmental level.

Stage 3:

At pre-test, four subjects (S2/M, S6/F, S9/M and S10/F) were at this developmental level. Moseley (2003) described this stage as one where to the reader, only “a few final consonants are known” (p.28). At post-test, two subjects S4/M and S5/M were at this stage, indicating a slight improvement in their word recognition and phonic skills from their previous Stage 2.

Stage 4:

At pre-test, none of the subjects was at this developmental level. At post-test, three subjects S1/M, S3/F and S8/F improved to this stage with S1/M making a significant improvement from Stage 1 (up by three levels) while the other two moved up from Stage 2 (up by two levels). Moseley (2003) described this stage as one where “short vowels are known in some words” (p.28).

Stage 5:

None of the subjects were at this developmental level at pre-test. At post-test, four of them - S2/M, S6/F, S7/F and S0/M - attained this stage, which according to Moseley (2003), is where “initial consonants and most final consonants are identified, while knowledge of consonant clusters is developing” (p.28).

Stage 6:

None of the subjects were at this developmental level at pre-test. Only one subject S10/F made it to this level at post-test. This is the phase when the subject is noted to have known common long vowel digraphs (Moseley, 2003).

Stages 7-10:

None of the subjects managed to reach these developmental levels at pre-test or post-test. Briefly, Moseley (2003) described each of these stages as follow: “More long vowel spelling patterns are known, including ‘*igh*’ and magic-‘*e*’ at Stage 7. All spelling patterns in one-syllable words are recognized, plus common prefixes and suffixes in two-syllable words at Stage 8. Secure knowledge of spelling patterns in two-syllable words, and in some three-syllable words is attained at Stage 9. Finally, at Stage 10, most spelling patterns in the English language are recognized” (p.28-29).

Conclusion

The main purpose of this study was to investigate whether teaching concrete poetry to a group of ten K-2 Chinese children with low oracy/literacy in English language – who would be at risk of failing in school once they moved on to Primary 1 the following year – would be an effective strategy to improve their word recognition. Since very little or none has been reported or published on using concrete poetry as a teaching strategy in mainstream and/or

special schools other than the author's (see Chia, 1991, 1993, 1994, 1995, 1996c, 2006), this study would be a significant, if not an additional, contribution to our pedagogical knowledge of employing such creative strategies to teach, in this case, word recognition to preschool children. The findings reported in this study show that concrete poetry had benefited the subjects' performance in word recognition. Their WRaPS-2 results showed a significant improvement in terms of their WR ages from pre-test (4 years 11 months) to post-test (6 years 3 months) with an increase by 1 year 3 months ($r = .80$). Similarly, their performance in the combined mean ROV/EOV standard scores (94.7/92.6 respectively) at post-test ($r = .84$) were better than the combined mean ROV/EOV standard scores (86.6/88 respectively) at pre-test ($r = .46$) with respective increases of 10.8/4.6 in ROV/EOV standard scores. Standard scores are chosen for comparison here because they have better correlation coefficients than raw scores and equivalent oral vocabulary ages. The mean General Vocabulary Composite was 92.4, average at post-test, up by 7.6 points from 84.8, below average at pre-test ($r = .63$). When examining the results of the post-test ROV and EOV separately, the findings suggest that the performance of these subjects in ROV standard scores ($r = .48$ at post-test) were better than their EOV standard scores ($r = .70$ at post-test). This interesting finding seems to suggest that concrete poetry is more effective in improving the receptive oral vocabulary than expressive oral vocabulary. One explanation why this is so could be that the meaning of a concrete poem visually expressed through its shape, size and physical layout of its letters enables the subjects to see, understand and remember better what it is like in their mind. The physical design of the concrete poem puts its form ahead of its content. In this way, its form helps them to understand the content of the word without having to describe it in so many words, and hence, a better receptive oral vocabulary. As the saying goes "a picture is worth a thousand words", this is probably very true here. Another explanation is that through enjoyment of creating their own concrete poems, these subjects learnt better and hence, were able to perform better in their word recognition.

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